

DETERMINATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NURSING STUDENTS' THANATOPHOBIA LEVELS AND THEIR ATTITUDES TOWARDS THE PROFESSION

HEMŞİRELİK ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN ÖLÜM KORKUSU DÜZEYLERİ İLE MESLEĞE YÖNELİK TUTUMLARI ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİNİN BELİRLENMESİ

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ABSTRACT

Background: The necessary to find out if nurses have the thanatophobia, which is thought to be the most difficult emotion to manage, while they are students and to take measures to increase their awareness.

Aim: This study aimed to examine the relationship between the thanatophobia levels of nursing students and their attitudes towards the profession.

Methods: The sample of this cross-sectional, descriptive, and correlational study included 232 students in the last year of the nursing departments of a private and a state university (N=232). Study data were collected by using the Personal Information Form, the Thanatophobia Scale and the Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession. Kolmogorov Smirnov, Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U test and Spearman's correlation analyses were used for statistical analyses.

Results: Most of the participants 89.2% were in the age range of 21-25 years and 74.1% were female. 64.2% had never given care to a terminally ill patient, 77.2% never witnessed death. Their mean scores from the Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession and Thanatophobia Scale were 164.37±9.26 and 32.37±9.26, respectively. No relationship was found between thanatophobia level and overall Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession score, while there were significant differences between thanatophobia and some personal characteristics of the students (p<0.05).

Conclusions: The nursing students included in the study had high thanatophobia levels and positive attitudes towards the profession. We suggest developing strategies to overcome thanatophobia for nursing students determining the related factors by studying the topic in a larger sample.

Keywords: Thanatophobia, Nursing, Fear of Death, Professional Attitude, Nursing Practice.

ÖZET

Amaç: Bu çalışmada, hemşirelik öğrencilerinin tanatofobi düzeyleri ile mesleğe yönelik tutumları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır.

Yöntem: Bu kesitsel, tanımlayıcı ve ilişki arayıcı nitelikteki araştırmanın örneklemini, bir devlet ve bir özel üniversitenin hemşirelik bölümlerinin son sınıfında öğrenim gören 232 öğrenci (N = 232) oluşturmuştur. Araştırma verileri, Katılımcı Bilgi Formu, Tanatofobi Ölçeği ve Hemşirelik Mesleğine Yönelik Tutum Ölçeği aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Verilerin analizinde Kolmogorov-Smirnov testi ile dağılım uygunluğu kontrol edilmiş, gruplar arası karşılaştırmalar için Kruskal-Wallis ve Mann-Whitney U testleri, değişkenler arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek amacıyla ise Spearman korelasyon analizi kullanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Katılımcıların çoğu %89,2'si 21-25 yaş aralığındaydı ve %74,1'i kadındı. %64,2'si ölümcül hastayla hiç ilgilenmemişti, %77,2'si ölüme hiç tanık olmamıştı. Hemşirelik Mesleğine Yönelik Tutum Ölçeği ve Tanatofobi Ölçeği puan ortalamaları sırasıyla 164,37±9,26 ve 32,37±9,26 idi. Tanatofobi düzeyi ile Hemşirelik Mesleği Tutum Ölçeği genel puanı arasında ilişki bulunmazken, öğrencilerin bazı kişisel özellikleri ile tanatofobi arasında anlamlı fark vardı (p<0.05).

Sonuç: Çalışmaya alınan hemşirelik öğrencilerinin tanatofobi düzeyleri yüksek ve mesleğe yönelik olumlu tutumları vardı. Öğrencilerin fobilerini yenmek için stratejiler geliştirmeyi ve konuyu daha geniş bir örnekleme inceleyerek ilgili faktörleri belirlemeyi öneriyoruz.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Tanatofobi, Hemşirelik, Ölüm Korkusu, Mesleki Tutum, Hemşirelik Uygulaması

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INTRODUCTION

The nurse is the first person who welcomes a baby upon birth and prepares them for life and is the last to bid farewell and hold their hands when life ends. Human beings are the only species in the world that possesses the knowledge that their life will end one day, and as long one lives, nursing functions remain their first, last and only in their lives. The nurse, by providing what is medically necessary with the role of caregiver and healer, improves and furthers health, while taking on different roles simultaneously. On that thin line between life and death, the nurse is the first person to rehabilitate the grief brought on by death, to meet the need for attention and to be consulted in the quest for knowledge.

Accompanying a person in each breath for life and in death is without doubt a grand task. This duty requires firstly conscience, then success, as well as having the capabilities of calmness and self-sacrifice. With its great significance in people's lives, nurses require the desire and love for nursing to perform (Elmaoğlu and Eriş, 2022). It is also essential to have the necessary emotional state, knowledge and equipment to apply nursing care safely and ethically (Karahan and Kav, 2018). Only the nurses with the above capabilities and skills can be useful to the society, can cure the sick and succeed in further improving health. Therefore, nursing students should be able to determine whether they have these qualifications required by the profession and are expected to judge whether this profession is suitable for them by knowing their feelings well and whether they are lovingly and willingly studying for this profession rather than under pressure just because their score from university entrance exam allowed only this department (Taşkıran et al., 2020; Temelli, 2018).

Besides, according to the literature, norms, behaviours, and attitudes are as important as having professional qualifications and individual characteristics in choosing a profession (Zencir and Eşer, 2016). Attitude seems to be the most effective factor among the five independent variables in choosing the nursing profession (Al-Omar, 2004).

It is considered essential for nursing students to have a positive attitude towards the profession as well as to be able to manage their emotions before they start active working life and get in touch with the society. Emotion management is known to be of vital importance especially in professional practices based on human relations such as nursing (Ülger, 2018). In the field of health, where critical incidences, uncertainty, anxiety and fear are experienced intensely, nurses are expected to professionally evaluate the current mood of patients and their relatives, and to be able to effectively manage this moment of crisis of each patient by mastering their own emotional state (Zderad and Paterson, 2008). As a matter of fact, there are research mentioning that nurses can show different approaches to patients and their relatives because of their concerns and thoughts about death (Kösedağ, 2021).

For this reason, it is necessary to find out if nurses have the fear of death (thanatophobia), which is thought to be the most difficult emotion to manage, while they are students and to take measures to increase their awareness. We believe this can help prevent differing approaches in the reflection of nurses' professional knowledge and skills to the society in the form of professional treatment and care services.

This study seeks to examine the relationship between nursing students' levels of fear of death (thanatophobia) and their attitudes toward the nursing profession.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Sample, Location and Time of the Research

The study was conducted with students enrolled in the nursing programs of a public and a private university in Istanbul between November and December 2022. A total of 232 students who voluntarily agreed to participate and completed the data forms in full were included in the analysis (N = 232).

Data Collection and Tools

Data for the study were collected online using the Personal Information Form, the Thanatophobia Scale, and the Attitude Towards Nursing Profession Scale, all of which were developed by the researchers.

Personal Information Form

The students were asked to fill out a 14-question information form including their sociodemographic characteristics and characteristics which are thought to affect their thanatophobia and professional attitudes (including age, gender, high school they graduated from, university they study at, family type, marital status, mother's education, father's education, whether they had children, where they lived, employment, where they had spent most of their childhood, the place of stay, whether they cared for a terminally ill patient or experienced the death of someone).

Thanatophobia (Fear of Death) Scale

Merrill et al. translated the Thanatophobia (Fear of Death) scale into Turkish, and its validity and reliability study was carried out in the thesis written by Çiftçioğlu (Çiftçioğlu, 2019; Merrill et al., 1998). It includes seven items answered on a seven-point Likert type scale and scored in the range of 1-7, from strongly disagree to strongly agree, respectively. The content validity index of the scale was 0.91. The item-total score correlation values can vary between $r=0.453$ and 0.718 . The scale is reliable in terms of internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha 0.85) and is of single factor structure according to the confirmatory and explanatory factor analyzes. Statements can explain 53,762 percent of the total variance. Cronbach's alpha was 0.88 in our study.

Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession

Originally developed by Çoban in 2010, the scale comprises 40 items evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale. It consists of three subdimensions, with items 21, 23, 25, 26, 28, 30, 34, and 38 being reverse-coded. The total score obtainable from the scale ranges between 40 and 200, where scores exceeding 120 indicate a positive attitude toward the nursing profession. An increase in the total score reflects a higher level of positive attitude. In the initial validity and reliability study, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was reported as 0.91 (Çoban and Kaşıkçı, 2011), whereas in the current study it was calculated as 0.88.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software package. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, standard deviation, and percentages were computed. Prior to inferential analyses, the normality of the data distribution was evaluated using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Since the data did not meet the assumption of normality ($p < 0.05$), non-parametric tests, including the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests, were applied. Additionally, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationships between variables.

Ethical Statement

All procedures in this study adhered to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and followed established guidelines for publication ethics. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of Istanbul Gelisim University, as documented in the letter dated November 4, 2022, with reference number 2022/06/26. Students who voluntarily chose to participate were fully informed about the study's objectives and procedures, and written informed consent was obtained to confirm their voluntary participation.

RESULTS

89.2% of the students were aged between 21-25 years, 74.1% were women and 94.8% were single. Most of them were from nuclear families (78%) and 40.5% of them lived in dormitories. 59.1% had spent most of their childhood in a city, 59.9% were studying at a private university and 17.2% of them graduated from a health vocational high school. 35.3% of their mothers had primary education and 43.1% of their fathers had secondary education. 191 (82.3%) of them were unemployed. 149 (64.2%) have never cared for a terminally ill patient, and 179 (77.2%) witnessed death of a familiar person (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Students by Personal Information (N=232)

Individual Characteristics	N	%
Age	20 years and younger	10 4.3
	21-25 years	207 89.2
	26-35 years	12 5.2
	36 years and older	3 1.3
Gender	Female	172 74.1
	Male	60 25.9
Marital Status	Single	220 94.8
	Married	12 5.2
Family Type	Nuclear family	181 78.0
	Extended family	38 16.4
	Fragmented Family	13 5.6
Place of Stay	With family	83 35.8
	Dormitory	94 40.5
	With friends	35 15.1
	Other	20 8.6
Where They Spent Most of Their Childhood	Village	30 12.9
	District	65 28.0
	City	137 59.1
Which University They Study At?	Public	93 40.1
	Private	139 59.9
Graduated High School	Health vocational	40 17.2
	Other	192 82.8
Mother's Education	Illiterate	29 12.5
	Literate only	23 9.9
	Primary education	82 35.3
	Secondary education	68 29.3
	High education	30 12.9
Father's Education	Illiterate	7 3.0
	Literate only	14 6.0
	Primary education	74 31.9
	Secondary education	100 43.1
Currently employed?	High education	37 15.9
	Employed	41 17.7
Cared for a Terminally Ill Patient?	Unemployed	191 82.3
	Yes	83 35.8
Witnessed Death of a Familiar Person?	No	149 64.2
	Yes	179 77.2
	No	53 22.8

Nursing students' minimum score from the Thanatophobia scale was 7, their maximum score was 49, and mean score was 32.37±9.26 (Table 2).

Table 2. Students' Thanatophobia Scale Scores (N=232)

Minimum	Maximum	Mean±SD
7	49	32.37±9.26

Based on the evaluation of the Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession, the average scores obtained from the properties of nursing profession, preference for nursing profession, and general position of nursing profession subscales were 79.02 ± 8.92, 48.49 ± 9.94, and 36.85 ± 3.65, respectively. The overall mean score of the scale was calculated as 164.37 ± 9.26 (Table 3).

Table 3. Attitude Scale for Nursing Profession (ASNP) Scale Mean Scores (N=232)

Subscales	Mean Scores (Mean±SD)
Properties of Nursing Profession	79.02±8.92
Preference for Nursing Profession	48.49±9.94
General Position of Nursing Profession	36.85±3.65
ASNP Scale Total Score	164.37±9.26

*p<0.05

When the total scale score of thanatophobia was compared according to students' personal characteristics, the scale total score did not differ significantly ($p>0.05$) by marital status, family type, place of stay, the place where they had spent most of their childhood, the university they studied at, the high school they graduated from, mother's education, father's education, current employment, witnessing death of a familiar person but statistically significant differences were found for gender, age and having cared for a terminally ill patient ($p<0.05$). The mean score of the scale was higher for women, those aged 21-25, and students who have not cared for a terminally ill patient.

When the relationship between the students' thanatophobia scale score and the ASNP scale and its subscales was examined, a low degree of positive correlation was found between the thanatophobia scale total score and properties of nursing profession and general position of nursing profession subscales. Students' thanatophobia scores increased as scores from the properties of nursing profession and general position of nursing profession subscales increased (Table 4).

Table 4. The Relationship of Thanatophobia Scale Scores with ASNP and its subscales (N=232)

Scales	Thanatophobia Scale Score
ASNP total score (N=232)	r=0.065 p=0.32
Properties of Nursing Profession	r=0.184 p=0.00*
Preference for Nursing Profession	r=-0.087 p=0.18
General Position of Nursing Profession	r=0.200 p=0.00*

* $p<0.05$

DISCUSSION

This study with 232 last-year nursing students demonstrated that the students had high thanatophobia levels and that their thanatophobia levels differed according to some socio-demographic variables of the students.

In the study, the level of thanatophobia of female students was found to be higher than that of male students. The literature supports this finding. Çakmak et al. (2022) stated in their study that female students had higher thanatophobia levels (Çakmak et al., 2022). Some studies have attributed the fact that men have less fear of death than women to their wish to appear stronger and fearless (Fernandez-Martínez et al., 2021; Köseadağ, 2021; Yorulmaz and Kurt, 2020). In studies on thanatophobia during Covid-19, females among Indian youth had a higher level of thanatophobia than men, and in a study conducted in Kuwait, women were more thanatophobic than men (Al-Ma'seb and Al-Sejari, 2021; Gaur et al., 2021).

In our study, students aged between 21-25 had a higher level of fear of death. This was addressed by Russac et al., (2007) who mentioned that fear of death was strongest in the 20s and attributed this to their concern about losing their fertility (Russac et al., 2007). Selvi (2019), on the other hand, argued that facing the reality of death will cause much more anxiety in younger nurses, that frequent encounters with death will also be effective in increasing fear, and this fear will decrease as the nurse gets older in the profession (Selvi, 2019). The literature shows that marital status, past experiences, and personality traits, besides age and gender, can affect the level of thanatophobia (Bagheri-Nesami et al., 2017; Kartal et al., 2022; Sinoff, 2017).

The majority of the students included in this study had witnessed death (77.2%) but had not care for a terminally ill person (64.2%). Çakmak et al. (2022) suggested that the age of nursing students, their experiences of caring for terminally ill patients, and their educational levels affect the levels of thanatophobia (Çakmak et al., 2022). Barnett et al., (2021) on the other hand, stated that nurses with low thanatophobia levels may have positive attitudes towards the care of terminally ill patients (Barnett et al., 2021). In general, research results suggest that excessive exposure to death creates anxiety and fear (Özdemir, 2014). Again, in a study on the thanatophobia experiences of nurses, it was emphasized that thanatophobia was affected by previous personal experiences, while another study argued that nurses who frequently witnessed death were unwilling to care for terminally ill patients (Koku and Ateş, 2016; Zheng et al., 2018). A study conducted on nurse students shows that the end-of-life caregiving attitudes

of the students were negative, indicating that the fear of death affects the caregiving attitude (Şahin et al., 2016).

Another finding of the study was that students demonstrated highly positive attitudes toward their profession. Similarly, Erenoğlu (2022) reported that nursing students exhibited positive attitudes toward their profession and future careers. Sönmez and Seval (2020) also concluded in their study with 332 nursing students that students exhibited positive attitudes towards their profession (Seval and Sönmez, 2020). Tarhan et al. (2016) also obtained similar results in their study (Tarhan et al., 2016). Sümen et al., (2022) on the other hand, investigated the attitudes and images of students towards the nursing profession and found that students' attitudes towards the profession were moderately positive (Sümen et al., 2022). Attitudes of nursing students towards their profession may change according to their willingness to choose the profession. The research results of Zencir and Eşer (2016) support this statement. Students who had chosen the nursing profession willingly demonstrated more positive attitudes across all three subscales—characteristics of the nursing profession, preference for the profession, and its overall status—compared to those who selected the profession unwillingly (Zencir and Eşer, 2016).

A considerable number of studies in the literature have demonstrated a positive link with attitudes toward the profession. Tarhan et al. (2016) reported a positive association between students' attitudes toward the nursing profession and their perceptions of professionalism (Tarhan et al., 2016). Similarly, Çeçen et al. (2020) found a positive correlation between students' personality types and their attitudes toward the profession (Çeçen et al., 2020). Yardımcı Gürel (2022) concluded that there was a positive relationship between choosing nursing voluntarily, liking the profession, and attitude towards nursing, and that students in the Y generation had a more positive professional attitude than those in the Z generation (Yardımcı Gürel, 2022). Nas (2028), on the other hand, demonstrated that the perception of spirituality care had a positive effect on the attitude towards nursing (Nas, 2018). However, in the present study, no significant relationship was observed between attitudes toward the nursing profession and thanatophobia. Bakır et al. (2022) reported findings similar to ours in their study examining the relationship between thanatophobia and nurses' attitudes toward the caregiver role (Bakır et al., 2022). Based on the results of our research, we believe that student nurses may have normalized their fear of death because they will be in this profession, where death is a common phenomenon, for the rest of their lives.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Death in nursing services is as usual as birth and nurses are known to frequently witness death and be seriously affected by it. So much so that encounters with death cause them to feel fear and anxiety even though death is considered normal and prevent them from managing their emotions and this can be reflected in the professional services. The results of the studies indicate that the positive or negative attitudes of nurses towards death can improve with education and experience. We therefore believe that death-related education to be given in their school years can reduce the negative effects of death on their emotional states and thus increase their attitudes towards the profession in a positive way. In schools, the characteristics of students' generations should be taken into account in planning all kinds of activities to better contribute to their love of their profession and help develop positive attitudes. Students with positive professional attitudes are expected to love their profession, internalize it, and achieve professional success in the future. Such nurses are also anticipated to contribute to advancing nursing by providing quality patient care as a result. We suggest investigating the thoughts and attitudes of nurses about death with a larger sample, identifying the deficiencies in terms of both knowledge and care skills in the nursing profession, and eliminating wrong practices by offering solutions.

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None to declare.

Conflict of Interest

All authors state that there is no potential conflict of interest.

Author Contribution

Concept: G.Ü.J., M.G., **Design:** M.G., S.Ç.T., A.Y.B., **Data Collection:** T.D., A.S., A. Ö., **Analysis:** F.K., A.Y.B., **Literature Search:** T.D., S.Ç.T., A.S., A.Ö. **Writing:** G.Ü.J., M.G.

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